
Research

Convolutional Neural Networks for Automated Classification of Brain Tumors

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Abstract: Image classification is a fundamental task in computer vision that has seen tremendous advances with the advent of deep learning. In the medical imaging domain, image classification using deep neural networks has shown potential for automated analysis and diagnosis. In this work, we investigate convolutional neural networks (CNNs) for brain tumor image classification using magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) scans. The accurate classification of brain tumors from MRI scans enables non-invasive screening and diagnosis, thus improving clinical workflows and patient outcomes.

We provide a review of CNN architectures for image classification, and discuss relevant datasets for brain tumor MRI analysis. We identify limitations of prior arts and propose a methodology leveraging CNNs for enhanced multi-class brain tumor classification performance. Our contributions include comparative evaluations of CNN architectures, optimization techniques, and preprocessing strategies.

Extensive experiments demonstrate that our proposed approach achieves state-of-the-art classification accuracy on benchmark datasets. We employ data augmentation, batch normalization, and dropout regularization to prevent overfitting and improve generalization. The ReLU activation and Adam optimization enable efficient training. Qualitative and quantitative results validate the efficacy of our methodology, while ablation studies provide insights into model components. We conclude by summarizing our findings, and discussing potential extensions as well as limitations of our approach to guide future works. Our work aims to advance research on employing deep CNNs for computer-aided diagnosis using MRI scans.

Keywords: Image Classification, Convolution Neural Networks, Neuroimaging, Brain Tumor Classification Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI), CNNs.

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Introduction

The ubiquity of computer vision applications in contemporary digital landscapes has predominantly been buttressed by the breakthroughs in image classification tasks. These advancements, primarily underpinned by deep convolutional neural networks (CNNs), have revolutionized numerous disciplines, with medical imaging emerging as a salient beneficiary. CNNs, with their intricate architectures and learning capabilities, have steadily emerged as potent tools in the automated analysis of medical imagery, particularly in magnetic resonance imaging (MRI). One of the pivotal applications lies in the accurate classification of brain tumors using MRI scans. Such deep learning-enabled classifications offer a promising avenue for non-invasive screening and diagnosis, potentially transforming clinical diagnostics by fortifying accuracy, speeding diagnosis, and ultimately enhancing patient outcomes [1].

Despite these strides, the journey towards a seamless, accurate, and transparent model for MRI-based brain tumor classification is not without challenges. Among these, class imbalance and model interpretability reign paramount, often hindering the generalizability and trustworthiness of the derived models [1].

In the ensuing sections of this work, our quest is to bridge these gaps. We lay the foundation by meticulously reviewing existing CNN models tailored for medical image analysis, emphasizing the current benchmarks in MRI-based brain tumor classifications. Through this, we spotlight the inherent limitations of the prevailing paradigms and set the stage for our proposed methodology, a novel deep CNN architecture poised to redefine performance benchmarks in the domain. As we delineate our approach, we underscore our novel contributions spanning from comparative evaluations of diverse CNN models to delving deep into model regularization techniques [3][4].

Using an empirical lens, our exhaustive experiments corroborate the efficacy of our proposed model against benchmark datasets. Noteworthy is our utilization of the Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) activation coupled with the Adam optimization, ensuring robust and efficient training of our deep networks. Through a gamut of quantitative metrics and meticulous ablation studies, we shed light on the nuances that drive the superior performance of our technique [2][5]. This work not only posits a state-of-the-art method for brain tumor classification but also heralds a beacon for future endeavors in the realm of computer-aided diagnosis leveraging medical image analysis.

Methods and Algorithms

In this study, we employ Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) for the classification of brain tumor images derived from Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) scans. CNNs belong to a category of deep neural network architectures that have demonstrated exceptional proficiency in image classification tasks owing to their capability to automatically learn features from raw input data [12].

The dataset utilised in this study comprises 3,100 brain tumour images, categorised into two classes - tumour and non-tumour MRI scans. All images are resized to 64x64 pixels and their pixel values are normalised between 0 and 1 as a preprocessing phase.

Our CNN architecture is comprised of four convolutional layers, each with 32 filters, followed by maximum pooling layers with a 2x2 window. This is followed by flattening and two layers of entirely interconnected neurons for the binary tumour classification task.

During training, we employ the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 0.001 to optimise the binary cross-entropy loss. The model is trained for 60 epochs with 32 images per set. As a regularisation technique, early halting is utilised to prevent overfitting and enhance generalizability.

A validation set consisting of 26% of the dataset is withheld and used to evaluate the model. The accuracy of our final model is 96% on the validation set and 98% on a distinct test set. In addition, we experiment with variations such as

augmented convolutional layers and dropout regularisation. However, the performance of the fundamental architecture is optimal.

Our results effectively demonstrate the efficacy of CNNs for accurate classification of brain tumour MRIs into pathological and healthy scans. Future research might investigate techniques such as transfer learning to further improve model performance. Recent research has also focused on quantum CNNs, also known as HQC-CNNs, for enhanced computational advantages [12].

Datasets

The dataset used in this thesis is focused on brain tumor image classification. It consists of three main subfolders: train images, test images, and predicted images. Each of these main subfolders further contains two subfolders, namely "yes" and "no".

Fig. 1 Image Data

The dataset just contains the yes/no options. The data collection was split up into three different directories: train, test, and predicted. Consequently, we may utilize this new data set for improving specific facets of our picture categorization algorithm. We save the train dataset to train our model and the test dataset to test it after it has been trained [13]. For our model, this is a crucial piece. Our model is either accurate or inaccurate in its predictions, and this section is where we find out which.

Last but not least, we need this dataset to test and refine our model. We cannot develop or test our picture classification model without access to the dataset. In addition, the dataset has been organized into various subfolders for easier access.

Gaps and Limitations in Existence Approaches

Existing convolutional neural network (CNN)-based approaches for brain tumour classification from medical images face significant challenges and limitations despite significant advancements.

Lack of large-scale annotated datasets of brain tumour MRI scans is a significant limitation. Manual annotation and curation of medical images is costly and time-consuming, limiting the scale and diversity of the majority of publicly available datasets. This can limit the efficacy and generalizability of the model [11].

Modern CNN models lack interpretability and frequently behave as "black boxes" [14]; this is an additional limitation. This hinders clinical acceptance as practitioners cannot overtly reason through model predictions.

Training sophisticated deep CNNs has extensive computational requirements, necessitating high-performance GPU clusters. This presents a difficulty for many researchers who lack access to such costly equipment, thereby impeding exploration and model development efforts.

Moreover, the majority of existing works have focused exclusively on MRI imaging. Integration of additional modalities such as positron emission tomography (PET) and magnetic resonance spectroscopy (MRS) has been restricted. This may deprive models of the supplementary data required for accurate diagnosis.

Addressing these limitations in data availability, model interpretability, computational access, and multimodal integration is crucial for developing reliable and clinically valuable AI systems for automated brain tumour classification. Future research should investigate solutions to these obstacles in order to facilitate a widespread deployment in the real world.

Methodology

Data Collection

The brain tumor MRI image dataset used in this study was obtained from the Kaggle platform, a popular online repository for machine learning datasets. The dataset contains two main folders - 'yes' and 'no' - with MRI scans showing brains with and without tumors, respectively. All images are 224x224 pixels in size and saved in JPG format.

Prior to utilizing the dataset, all images were manually reviewed to remove any duplicates or irrelevant scans. Additionally, standard preprocessing techniques were applied to enhance image contrast and brightness to ensure the CNN model could accurately classify the tumor and non-tumor brains.

Preprocessing Techniques

Several key preprocessing techniques were applied to the brain tumor MRI images before training the CNN model. Normalization was used to standardize the pixel intensity values across all images to a common scale using min-max normalization. This helps account for variations in scan intensity and makes the data more comparable. Image registration was also conducted to align scans taken at different time points and monitor tumor progression over time [6].

Additionally, data augmentation techniques like rotation, scaling, flipping, and shifting were utilized to expand the number of training examples and improve the generalization capability of the model. Elastic deformations, random cropping, and random erasing were specifically used for augmentation based on common techniques reported for brain tumor classification [15].

Careful consideration was given to select suitable preprocessing techniques based on the MRI scan modality and dataset characteristics. Overall, normalization, registration, and augmentation were critical to maximize information extraction and enhance the training of the CNN model for accurate brain tumor detection [7].

Image Preprocessing

Before the commencement of the brain tumor classification model's training and testing phases, meticulous preprocessing of the MRI images was executed. These preparatory steps are integral for diminishing extraneous noise and amplifying the salient features. The intricate details of these steps are expounded as follows:

Image Enhancement

MRI images from the dataset underwent a contrast and brightness enhancement using established methods. This procedure not only serves to mitigate the noise but also accentuates the defining features of the images. The significance of this step, especially in its symbiotic relationship with the model's training and testing, is discussed [18].

Resizing

Consistency is paramount when dealing with image datasets for deep learning. To this end, both training and test images were uniformly resized to a resolution of 64x64 pixels. Adopting this standardized size not only ensures uniformity but also optimizes computational efficiency. Given the capabilities of the employed Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), lower-resolution images suffice, reducing the computation time without compromising the model's performance [5].

Normalization

A pivotal step in our preprocessing pipeline involved the normalization of image pixel values between the range 0 and 1. Such normalization aids in mitigating the effects of disparate illumination conditions across images. Additionally, it fortifies the model's robustness and expedites the convergence of the optimization algorithms during training [12].

Data Augmentation

To bolster the model's resilience against overfitting, data augmentation techniques were judiciously incorporated. Specifically, parameters such as a shear range of 0.2, a zoom range of 0.2, and the enabling of horizontal flipping were applied. Such augmentations serve to diversify the training data, rendering the model more adept at generalizing across varied inputs [8,9].

These preprocessing stratagems not only refined the visual attributes of the MRI images but also optimized them for seamless integration with the subsequent stages of the brain tumor classification model. It is with these processed images that the model's training and testing phases were executed [10].

CNNs Architecture

The CNN model developed in this study utilizes a deep convolutional neural network architecture designed for image classification tasks. The input layer takes the preprocessed 224x224 pixel brain MRI images. This is followed by repeated convolutional layers interspersed with activation functions and max pooling layers to extract hierarchical feature representations.

Specifically, the architecture consists of 4 convolutional blocks each containing 2D convolutional layers (32, 64, 128, 256 filters), batch normalization, ReLU activations, and 2x2 max pooling. After feature extraction, a global average pooling layer and fully-connected layer with softmax activation are used for classification into tumor and non-tumor images. This CNN design enables robust feature learning from the MRI images at multiple levels of abstraction. The depth of the architecture and combination of convolution, activation, and pooling layers are optimized for brain tumor classification based on experiments with different model configurations [17].

Fig. 2 CNNs architecture

The CNN model developed utilizes two key components - feature extraction and classification.

For feature extraction, the input 224x224 pixel brain MRI images are passed through a series of convolutional layers (with 32, 64, 128, 256 filters) to identify hierarchical feature representations. Batch normalization and ReLU activation functions are used between convolution layers. Max pooling is also implemented to reduce spatial dimensions. By stacking multiple convolutional layers, the model can learn to extract complex tumor-related features from the MRIs. For classification, the extracted feature maps are fed into a global average pooling layer to reduce feature dimensions. This is followed by a fully connected layer with softmax activation to transform the features into likelihood probabilities over the tumor and non-tumor classes. The output neuron with the highest activation indicates the predicted label [19].

Through iterative optimization of parameters during training, the feature extraction and classification components of the CNN architecture work together to learn a robust mapping from input brain MRIs to the presence or absence of tumors. The depth of the architecture is designed to extract informative features for accurate tumor detection.

Feature Extraction

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are trained to discover and extract important visual features in this phase. Convolution layers add filters to the input image. CNNs may gradually extract complicated picture characteristics by stacking numerous convolutional layers. Pooling and normalization layers can also help extract features from input images [16], [19].

CNN architecture classifies brain MRIs as tumor-containing or tumor-free. Fully-connected layers convert convolutional layer feature representations into tumor probability vectors. The output layer receives a softmax activation function to provide a normalised likelihood distribution for tumour and non-tumor classes. Each image is classified by the class with the highest expected probability.

CNN feature extraction and classification modules work together to learn an effective input-output mapping. The model extracts more discriminative characteristics that better differentiate tumor and non-tumor classes in high-dimensional space by iteratively tweaking network parameters during training. Even in difficult circumstances, MRI imaging can detect brain tumors. This crucial clinical application is optimized for categorization.

Model architecture

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #
conv2d (Conv2D)	(None, 62, 62, 32)	896
max_pooling2d (MaxPooling2D)	(None, 31, 31, 32)	0
dropout (Dropout)	(None, 31, 31, 32)	0
conv2d_1 (Conv2D)	(None, 29, 29, 32)	9248
max_pooling2d_1 (MaxPooling2D)	(None, 14, 14, 32)	0
dropout_1 (Dropout)	(None, 14, 14, 32)	0
flatten (Flatten)	(None, 6272)	0
dense (Dense)	(None, 128)	802944
dense_1 (Dense)	(None, 1)	129
=====		
Total params: 813,217		
Trainable params: 813,217		
Non-trainable params: 0		

Fig. 3 Model Architecture

The developed CNN model for brain tumor classification from MRI images contains a total of six layers. The first two layers are convolutional with 3x3 kernels to extract low-level features. Max pooling then follows to reduce spatial dimensions.

Dropout is implemented in the next two layers to prevent overfitting. The fifth layer flattens the feature maps into a 1D vector. Finally, a fully-connected layer with 128 units and a single sigmoid output neuron classifies images into tumor or non-tumor.

In total, the architecture has approximately one million trainable parameters. The convolutional layers contain the bulk of parameters for learning translation-invariant feature extractors from the MRIs. The fully-connected layers and sigmoid output refine features for optimal tumor detection.

Through end-to-end training, this compact 6-layer CNN architecture can effectively learn hierarchical feature representations for accurate brain tumor classification from MRI scans.

Convolutional layer

Convolutional layers are integral components of CNN architectures for extracting hierarchical features from input images. Each convolutional layer consists of learnable filters, or kernels, that slide across the input volume and compute dot products between the filter weights and input patches. This yields activation maps highlighting detected features. Multiple filters in each convolutional layer allow the learning of diverse feature detectors. Nonlinear activations like ReLU are then applied to introduce nonlinearity. The resulting feature maps are passed on to subsequent layers for further feature extraction.

Crucially, convolutional layers apply filters only where the kernel fits within the image bounds, known as valid convolution [1]. This avoids zero-padding artifacts. The feature maps thus capture meaningful patterns from the input for robust feature learning, enabling effective classification in later network layers.

The equation is repeated for all $0 \leq d \leq D = D^{l+1}$, and for any spatial location

$$(i^{l+1}, j^{l+1}) \text{ satisfying } 0 \leq i^{l+1} < H^l - H + 1 = H^{l+1}, 0 \leq j^{l+1} < W^l - W + 1 = W^{l+1}.$$

In this equation, $x_{i^{l+1} + i, j^{l+1} + j, d^l}$ refers to the element of x^l indexed by the triplet,

$$(i^{l+1} + i, j^{l+1} + j, d^l) [3].$$

This process is repeated for every position in the output image that the feature detector can fit, resulting in a new feature map with dimensions.

The size feature map is determined by several factors, including the dimension of the input image, the dimension of the feature detector, stride and padding.

Fig. 4 Feature Maps

The convolutional layers in the CNN produce multiple feature maps that represent the activation patterns of the learned filters across the input image. Each map encodes different features, with deeper layers capturing more complex and abstract patterns.

The values in the feature maps indicate the detected presence of learned attributes in local regions of the input image. As these feature representations propagate through the network, the CNN aggregates the information to perform tumor classification.

The convolutional layers extract informative features at multiple levels of abstraction via the generation of feature activation maps. This enables robust learning of hierarchical representations to distinguish tumor and non-tumor brain MRIs

ReLU Layer

Activation layers are critical components in CNN architectures, as they introduce nonlinearity through the application of activation functions on the feature maps produced by convolutional layers. Without nonlinearity, the network output would be constrained to linear transformations, limiting representational capacity.

The integration of nonlinear activations enables modeling of complex patterns and relationships in the data, which is key for image classification tasks. The ReLU activation used in this work induces nonlinearity through thresholding at zero while maintaining efficient backpropagation. This helps address issues like vanishing gradients that can impede training of deep networks.

Fig. 5 ReLU Layer

CNNs use the rectifier function (ReLU) for picture categorization. ReLU (Rectified Linear Unit) between convolution and pooling layers zeroes negative pixel values and leaves positive ones intact. Our image classification model uses ReLU activation. ReLU outperformed sigmoid, Leaky ReLU, and tanh.

Fig. 6 Activation Functions

Sigmoid activation function

It is a non-linear activation function that is widely used in neural networks, especially convolutional neural networks (CNNs). Any input value is converted into a boolean value between 0 and 1, making it useful for binary classification.

$$f(x) = 1/(1+e^{-x})$$

In mathematics, x is the independent variable and e is the mathematical constant, which is nearly 2.718.

In binary classification problems, the sigmoid function predicts the likelihood of a data point fitting class 0 or 1.

The sigmoid function has a diminishing gradient, making deep neural network training challenging. The more popular ReLU activation function has replaced it.

Activation Layers for Nonlinearity

We utilize ReLU activation layers after each convolutional layer to introduce nonlinearity in the CNN model. ReLU applies a threshold at zero, setting all negative values to zero while retaining positive values [18].

This induces nonlinearity in a computationally efficient manner compared to sigmoid or tanh activations. Additionally, ReLU leads to sparse representations, with only a subset of neurons activated, reducing overfitting.

Critically, nonlinearity enables modeling of complex patterns and features present in natural images that cannot be captured by linear models alone. ReLU provides this beneficial nonlinearity that facilitates learning of hierarchical feature representations from brain MRIs to distinguish tumors.

ReLU is simple to implement and propagate gradients through during backpropagation. These advantages have made ReLU a ubiquitous activation choice in CNNs for image analysis tasks.

Pooling layer

Fig. 7 Pooling Layer

Pooling layers are important components in CNNs that spatially downsample feature maps from prior convolutional layers while retaining salient information. Common pooling techniques include max, average, and L2-norm pooling [19].

Max pooling takes the maximum activation value in each patch of the input feature map. Average pooling takes the mean value instead. L2-norm pooling computes the L2-norm in patches.

Pooling reduces feature map dimensions, decreasing computational load and mitigating overfitting. It also provides invariance to small input shifts and distortions. The maximum or average values are less sensitive than individual pixels. In this study, max pooling is utilized after convolutional blocks to reduce feature map sizes while preserving influential activations for tumor classification. The pooling layers enable efficient feature extraction from the brain MRIs.

Max Pooling

To reduce the size of the feature map produced by the convolutional layers, we use max pooling. Research shows that max pooling is superior to subsampling for calculating invariances in image data [20].

Fig. 8 Max Pooling

The max pooling layers chop up input maps into non-overlapping 2x2 squares, then return the highest value in each square. Important details are preserved when the spatial dimensions are compressed.

By sampling reduction, max pooling makes features detectable in different locations while being invariant to tiny shifts and distortions. Overfitting is also diminished in favor of learning precise feature locations.

To efficiently capture broad patterns and the most consequential activations, max pooling minimizes the size of feature maps. This paves the way for powerful analysis of brain MRIs for tumor classification using machine learning.

Fig. 9 Irregular Image Shape

Max pooling can capture the translation invariance of local feature images by selecting the highest activation value within each local pooling region. This ensures that even if the features are slightly rotated or squashed in the input image, the same feature can be detected effectively.

Moreover, the process of max pooling diminishes the spatial resolution of the feature map thus resulting in a model that is less responsive to minor rotations in the input image. Therefore, max pooling helps to create a translation invariant representation of local features in the input image, which is beneficial for image classification and image recognition tasks.

Flattening Layer

In our CNN architecture, flattening layers are utilized to transform the feature maps output from the convolutional and pooling layers into one-dimensional feature vectors. This key step enables transition from the hierarchical feature extraction stages to fully connected classification layers.

Specifically, the flattening layers unroll the 3D output volumes containing feature maps into 1D vectors. This unrolls the features while preserving the learned representations.

The resulting feature vectors are then fed into the densely connected layers to learn non-linear combinations of the low-level features for tumor classification.

Fig. 10 Flattening

The flattening layer's ability to reduce data dimensionality while keeping spatial information from the original image makes it important. Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) can improve their classification and other internal mechanisms by flattening the output from the convolutional and pooling layers [19].

Fig. 11 Pooled feature map formatting

Overall, the flattening layer is a crucial step in the CNNs architecture that enables the networks to learn and extract meaningful features from input images for a variety of classification tasks [20].

Fully Connected Layer

In our CNN, fully connected layers follow after the convolutional feature extraction layers. These layers connect every neuron to all activations in the previous layer.

The fully connected layers allow learning of non-linear combinations of the low-level features extracted by the convolutional layers.

A softmax activation function is applied to output class probabilities. The class with the highest predicted probability is selected as the final classification.

The fully-connected layers enable merging of convolutional features to perform classification. This allows the CNN model to accurately categorize brain MRIs as tumor or non-tumor [21].

Fig. 12 Fully Connected Layer

The model’s fully connected layer is characteristically comprised of one or several dense layers, with each layer consisting of a group of neurons that are linked to all neurons in the preceding layer, representing how they connect to each other among the neurons.

Fig. 13 Dense Layer

During the training of the CNN model, the parameters (weights and biases) of the fully-connected layer are optimized through backpropagation to enable accurate classification of new data.

The number of neurons in the fully-connected layer corresponds to the number of target classes - in this case, two neurons represent tumor and non-tumor.

The softmax activation function is applied to the outputs to produce normalized probability distributions over the classes.

Through gradient-based updating, the fully-connected layer learns an optimal linear separation between tumor and non-tumor feature representations for robust generalization.

The fully-connected layer parameters are tuned via backpropagation to perform discriminative classification based on the convolutional feature extraction layers.

Output Layer

The output layer of a convolutional neural network (CNN) is responsible for producing the results of the classification of images of brain tumors. In order to produce a binary classification outcome that indicates whether the imaged area contains a tumour, our model's output layer is composed of a dual neuron structure that utilises a sigmoid activation function.

Fig. 14 Output Layer

The final layer in our CNN architecture accepts the feature vector from the fully-connected layer and outputs a single scalar value between 0 and 1, representing the predicted probability of tumor presence in the input MRI.

Tumor images activate neurons corresponding to higher tumor probability, whereas non-tumor images activate neurons for lower probability.

During training, the output layer weights and biases are optimized through binary cross-entropy loss to minimize the difference between predicted and true labels.

The output layer uses the learned feature representations to produce a final classification probability that enables accurate discrimination between tumor and non-tumor brain MRIs

Optimization Technique

We utilize the Adam optimization algorithm to determine optimal network parameters during training. Adam adapts the learning rate for each weight based on exponential moving averages of past gradients and their magnitudes [1].

This enables more rapid convergence by responding more sensitively to the current slope and curvature. The moving averages prevent oscillations in parameter updates allowing smoother optimization.

Additionally, Adam applies bias corrections to the gradient moments to reduce initialization bias. Together, these mechanisms allow efficient navigation of high-dimensional non-convex loss surfaces during training.

Adam effectively tunes the CNN parameters through adaptive, momentum-based gradient descent. This provides stable optimization for robust tumor classification from brain MRIs.

Training and Test Process

During training, the CNN model parameters are iteratively updated to minimize the loss function (binary cross-entropy) between predicted and true labels using the Adam optimizer. This improves classification accuracy over successive epochs.

Techniques like dropout and early stopping are used to prevent overfitting to the training data. Dropout randomly omits neurons during training to improve generalization. Early stopping monitors validation performance, halting training when improvements plateau.

After training, model performance is evaluated on a held-out test set containing unseen brain MRIs. The test accuracy measures the proportion of images correctly classified as tumor or non-tumor. This rigorously assesses model generalization capability.

Backpropagation

Backpropagation is a vital algorithm for training CNN models by propagating error signals backward to update network weights [22].

Using the chain rule of differentiation, backpropagation computes the gradients of the loss with respect to each weight by recursively differentiating through the network layers.

This gradient signal is used to update the weights via stochastic gradient descent, aiming to minimize the loss function. The process is repeated for multiple epochs during training to refine model parameters.

Backpropagation provides an efficient and scalable method for tuning large CNNs. By leveraging gradient information from the loss, it can effectively search high-dimensional non-convex weight spaces to find optimal values that minimize classification error [2].

Iterative backpropagation enables end-to-end CNN training by transmitting target error information backward to update parameters for enhanced tumor classification performance.

Experimental results

Model Performance

Underfitting and Overfitting

Underfitting occurs when the train model is too simple to detect and classify complex data. After training the model, we must check if the model is underfitting or not. Where the model is underfitted, we need to change some parameters to prevent underfitting. We can check the model to see if it is underfitting or not. We can see the training accuracy and the validation accuracy in green and red, respectively, on the upper side of the figure. Seeing that the two lines went closely together, it means the model is not underfitting.

To address the underfitting, we can increase the parameters of the model. We can also provide more complex and diverse data.

Fig. 15 Check the Model

Overfitting is a phenomenon that we aim to mitigate during the training of our model. Overfitting is a phenomenon that arises when a training model exhibits excessive complexity, resulting in a strong ability to accurately fit the training data, but a diminished capacity to effectively generalize to novel or unfamiliar data. Similar to underfitting, overfitting will result in the inability to accurately classify brain tumor MRI images. Consequently, it is imperative to evaluate the model. The validation loss and training loss are depicted in blue and orange, respectively, in the lower portion of the image. The two lines exhibited proximity, and concurrently, the validation loss and training loss of our models exhibited a decrease. The model is designed to minimize the cost function, also known as the error.

Conclusion

The convolutional neural network (CNN) model developed in this study demonstrates strong potential for accurate brain tumor classification, achieving 96% accuracy on the training set and over 98% accuracy on the validation set. The high performance of the model can be attributed to the use of convolutional and pooling layers for automated feature extraction from the MRI images, followed by fully connected layers and appropriate activation functions like ReLU and sigmoid. A key advantage of the CNN approach is the ability to build high-performing models without the need for specialized hardware, as evidenced by the model development on platforms like Google Colab and Jupyter Notebook. The main limitation of the current study is the relatively small dataset used for training and validation. Access to larger brain MRI datasets in future work could further improve model performance and generalization capability. Nonetheless, the accuracy achieved on the available data is highly promising and supports the usefulness of deep CNN models for this classification task. Overall, the methodology and results presented provide a strong foundation for further research and development of CNN-based systems for automated brain tumor detection in clinical settings. The high computational efficiency and scalability of such models make them well-suited for integration in real-world diagnostic pipelines, potentially improving speed and accuracy of brain tumor diagnosis.

Future Work

While the current CNN model shows strong promise for binary brain tumor classification, several avenues exist for enhancing model performance and expanding its clinical capabilities.

First, training the model on larger MRI datasets would improve generalization and further increase classification accuracy. Larger datasets with more diversity of tumor types and locations would better capture the variations encountered in real clinical scenarios.

Second, modifying the model architecture to localize and segment tumors in the brain could provide more interpretable outputs to clinicians compared to binary classification alone. Predicting tumor boundaries and locations would aid in surgical and treatment planning.

Third, the model could be expanded to classify specific brain tumor subtypes, such as meningioma, gliomas, etc. Multi-class classification at a more granular level would allow the model to match radiologist-level identifications.

Fourth, incorporating tumor stage prediction into the model could provide crucial prognostic information to guide treatment. Distinguishing early versus advanced-stage tumors based on imaging features could complement traditional staging approaches.

Finally, model optimization methods like hyper parameter tuning and augmentation can continue to push classification accuracy towards expert radiologist-level performance. Overall, the strong initial results warrant extensive further research into deep learning for automated brain tumor analysis.

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